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Machine Learning, BIM, and Strategic Management for Effective Project Planning, Execution and Safety

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Abstract: The execution of projects gets adversely affected or thwarted by planning and safety inadequacies. This study demonstrates that the inadequacies can be addressed significantly by combining Machine Learning (ML), Building Information Modeling (BIM) and Strategic Management (SM) in the processes of planning and managing construction projects. The proposed trio approach is integrative, technology-driven, result-oriented, and problem-solving. It promises tangible solutions to issues of decision-making, projection, design, budgeting, estimation, costing, and safety concerns, among others, which constrain efficient planning, management, execution and safety of construction projects. The study concludes that the combination of the three systems can ensure efficient and sustainable planning, execution and safety of projects. It recommends imbibing of the proposed integrative measure, increased stakeholder engagement, interdisciplinary collaboration among professionals, re/training, and policy options as the panacea.

Keywords: Machine learning, BIM, Strategic management, Project, Safety

Introduction

With Machine Learning (ML), Building Information Modeling (BIM) and Strategic Management (SM), many of the problems confronting construction industry can be addressed significantly. The problems include poor planning, delay, cost overrun, stakeholders' clashing interests and attitude, inefficient risk and human management, poor performance, and the sustenance of traditional methods of operations over the digital ones (Ogirri, 2024a&b; EL Mounla et al., 2023; Salako, 2023; Hadi, 2020). Combining the three mechanisms would lead to efficient planning and execution of construction projects. Studies confirm that BIM can function maximally and cause efficient service delivery in construction (Ogirri, 2024b; Hadi, 2020; Zeb et al., 2019; Rezaei et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2017). It is observed that many companies are yet to understand the benefits of using BIM (McGrawHill Construction, 2014).

To ensure a significant understanding of the benefits, the awareness level has to be increased through research and other practicable means. The present research is an attempt in that direction. BIM coordinates design efficiently and sustainably. This means that BIM is of ultimate value to the construction industry. It is a cutting-edge innovation fostering and promoting sustainability in the construction industry. ML is likewise. Samimpay and Saghatforoush (2020) aver that to attain significant feats in the construction industry, BIM has to be applied sustainably, as doing so would increase the contributions of the sector to the socio-economic development of society. Also, Liu et al. (2017) note that BIM guarantees efficient integration and delivery of projects. This assertion suggests that the application of BIM can lead to efficiency in different projects, including construction projects.

Also, studies affirm the viability of SM in the attainment of efficiency in various activities, including projects. Such studies include Bagader and Sultan (2022), Torzhevskaja (2017), and Kanyora and Okello (2015). More so, Kamble and Gaikwad (2024), Singh (2024), Akinloye and Shawana (2023), George et al. (2022), Shawana (2022), Srivastava (2021), Yigitcanlar et al. (2020) and Jarrahi (2018) show that AI technologies can ensure safety, and efficient management of risks and different activities. Obiuto et al. (2024) prove the benefits of AI in terms of efficiency, cost reduction, and planning and performance optimization. Since AI technologies are proven to facilitate detection and prediction of safety threats (Juhrich, 2023), there is no doubt that ML can be leveraged alongside BIM and SM for efficient planning, execution and safety of projects.

Machine Learning in Construction Projects

Construction is one of the spheres that Machine Learning (ML) can help address the inherent issues. With the prediction, detection and safety potentials of AI affirmed in the literature (Juhrich, 2023; Bidhendi & Azizi, 2021), this study argues that ML can be leveraged in combination with BIM and SM for solutions to problems or risks that unsophisticated and conventional techniques cannot help address. There is no doubt that Machine Learning (ML), like other subfields or models of artificial intelligence (AI), offer huge innovations to various spheres (Akter, 2024; Onifade & Alola, 2022). ML is

proven to be cost-effective (Oyeyemi et al., 2024; George et al., 2022). It has the following major models or techniques: supervised learning, unsupervised learning and reinforced learning. These can be leveraged for cost-effectiveness in planning and managing projects from the beginning to the end. Digital Image Analysis and Canny Edge Detector smart technologies can maximize the monitoring of safety (Alsakka et al., 2023; Baduge et al., 2022). This means that they can be leveraged for effective management of construction projects, from planning to execution phases and beyond to the safety phase.

Kalnawat's et al. (2024) study demonstrates the capacity of machine learning in safeguarding critical infrastructure from cyber threats. Being capable of safeguarding critical infrastructure implies that ML can also foster efficiency in planning, execution and safety of construction projects through its security techniques. This is because safety allows for efficiency in carrying out different tasks. Okusi's (2024) study proves that machine learning and AI have the capacity to detect, predict, resist and prevent threats to critical infrastructure; optimize the safety of critical infrastructure through automated and effective management of risks; create high level of awareness about how to optimally maintain critical infrastructure; and simulate and train human employees in the industry. These noted capabilities are considered by this study when proposing the combination of ML with BIM and SM for efficiency in construction project planning, execution and safety.

Thapaliya and Bokani (2024) show that machine learning, deep learning, and natural language processing are AI techniques that can adequately tackle cyber security threats; identify the patterns of malicious activities in comparison with the legitimate ones; empower security systems with large data in real-time; and automate incident response processes that allow for proactive actions and efficient quelling of risks. The implication of the foregoing is that ML can undertake the aforementioned tasks in the context of project planning, execution and safety too. Thuraka et al. (2024) discuss the place of AI and strategic management in the success of various critical projects. The study proposes the combination of the two sets of strategies for the attainment of successes in project planning, execution, maintenance and sustenance. The study is more like the present one in its proposal. While it proposes the combination of AI and SM, the present study proposes the combination of ML, BIM and SM for the attainment of effective planning, execution and safety of construction projects.

Similarly, Zhang et al. (2019) prove that through random forests and support vector machines, ML fosters efficiency and accuracy in predictive maintenance. Predictive maintenance is the practice of using real-time data and historical records to predict possible equipment failure and proffer remedy before time (Carvalho et al., 2019). AI-driven predictive maintenance seamlessly, timely and proactively examines, predicts and detects the conditions of assets without waiting until the fixed schedules, thereby preventing failures, breakdowns, unnecessary interventions and the possible effects of failures on safety and service delivery. Also, ML models have the capacity to process large amounts of data, with which they identify patterns and looming equipment failures (Okusi, 2024). Neural networks can

capture more complex failure modes. Although these are models of deep learning (DL), they have bearing to ML, because DL is a subfield or part of ML. The ability to capture complex failures make them more effective in handling large volumes of datasets in construction, as in other sectors (Pasupuleti et al., 2024; Ren et al., 2021).

ML and Deep Learning (DL) algorithms are proven by Jian-hua Li (2021) to be impacting internet world in a significant magnitude. They also observe that although the high time-consumption of Support Vector Machine (SVM) limits its detective capacity, AVL Tree can be used to reduce time and improve detection, prevention, and performance. The impact obtains in the construction sector. To increase the impact, this study proposes the combination of ML with BIM and SM in project planning, execution and safety. The study carried out by Kaur et al. (2023) affirms that ML, deep neural networks, decision trees, and web-log-based detection models can detect and predict XSS attacks. Their study also agrees with the stance of the present study that ML can play a critical role in ensuring safety and efficient project planning and execution. In the same vein, Okusi (2023) shows that deep forest is a technique of the ML that can help detect and prevent XSS attacks and address the issues of class imbalance. The listed techniques are to ML.

It is also quite interesting that Zhang et al. (2019) prove that reinforcement learning and other techniques of the ML algorithms allow systems to learn from data and improve overtime. This would breed efficiency in security, planning and execution of construction projects. Wusu et al. (2022) demonstrate that various ML algorithms are used for analytic prediction. This means that ML can be used to predict project situations during planning through the execution phases. With the predictive and decision-support algorithms of ML, the following are attained: efficiency, saving costs, time and resources, fostering better utilization, and preventing many mistakes, errors, faults and risks. In particular, the different techniques of ML, such as data-based method, SVM, NB, KNN, RF, AR algorithms, EL, k-Means clustering, and PCA, can be used for various security purposes. Thus, they can be used to ensure safety. ML alongside other AI technologies and techniques offers efficiency, safety, innovation and enhancement of different activities for optimal performance, productivity and outcomes (Regona et al., 2022).

Also, ML offers learning, innovation and career opportunities, including technology literacy skills. With these skills acquired, different persons involved in the task of quelling cyber security threats are bound to proficiently and significantly tackle the worrisome trends of cyber security threats (Adeniyi & Okusi, 2024). On the other hand, the key disadvantages include data incompleteness, scalability of models, needing a high volume of time for training, the cumbersome nature of ML and other AI models, and ethical issues like exhibition of bias (Adeniyi, 2024). According to Jian-hua Li (2021), Tariq et al. (2021), Kaur and Singh (2019), and Zhou and Wang (2019), ML techniques are inefficient in detecting and preventing cyber security threats, such as XSS attacks. To that end, combining ML with BIM and SM can help make up for the pitfalls of ML.

BIM in Construction Projects

Building Information Modeling (BIM) refers to a computer-aided technology for managing construction project information, focusing on building information, models, production, communication and analysis. According to Shahhosseini et al. (2014), BIM refers to a method of receiving information about construction projects in the design and pre-construction phases. For the present study, BIM is an AI-driven technology for optimized and digitalized construction and management of projects, buildings and other critical infrastructure in the construction sector. This study argues that to get more result in using BIM for construction, ML and SM should be combined with it. When combined, SM can foster efficient use and management of BIM, while ML and BIM can automate and optimize management processes and undertakings in the construction industry.

The examples of BI include: (i) WUFI, Tally, (ii) SketchUp, Tally, (iii) OpenStudio, Autodesk Insight, ClimateStudio, (iv) Autodesk Revit, Tally, (v) Miro, Enscape, (vi) Autodesk Revit, Rhino, and (vi) Enscape, Rhino (Ogirri, 2024b). BIM can be used variously. It can be used for design, planning, construction, operation, repair, maintenance, demolition and promote sustainability (McArthur, 2015; Wong & Zhou, 2015). BIM plays a critical role in design and manufacturing, logistic planning, assembly planning, construction control, project management, and maintenance of infrastructure (Hadi, 2020). That is, BIM is essential in construction projects, because it improves operational efficiency, and enhances and increases project sustainability. It also optimizes construction processes, allowing for streamlines design and manufacturing processes.

Besides, BIM ensures environment-friendly operations, and encourages significant collaboration among stakeholders. More so, the use of BIM leads to minimized errors and rework. BIM also plays a crucial role in planning, accuracy, and timely execution of projects. BIM ensures effective planning because its usage allows for early design, analysis, predictions, and orientation. With these, informed decisions are made. Nevertheless, there are different factors that constrain BIM adoption, integration and sustained use in the construction sector. The constraints are broadly classified into four main categories: technical, skill acquisition and training, legal procedures, and economic challenges (Dakhil & Alshawi, 2014). These constraints, among others, hamper significant integration of BIM into construction.

Dalui et al. (2021) examine the constraints to BIM adoption and implementation in UK. The results of their analysis reveal that the major constraints include the unwillingness of many professionals to key into the innovation, costs of software, cost implications and frequency of maintenance, lack of enthusiasm for the potential opportunities of BIM, environmental conditions, and cultural factors like belief or worldview about BIM as well as the like innovations in society. Since the benefits of BIM in construction outweigh its shortcomings (Hadi, 2020), it is important to adopt and use BIM in construction at a significant extent. To get the best out its adoption in the industry, it should be

combined with ML and SM, especially in the planning, execution and safety phases of construction projects.

Strategic Management in Construction Projects

The study by Alotaibi et al. (2024) affirms the importance of adopting BIM in the management of construction projects, with a view to enhancing legal and contractual management of projects. It emphasizes that adopting BIM for this purpose enhances collaboration among stakeholders involved in the projects, which thereby leads to a successful execution. For the study, BIM in this kind of management is beneficial because it helps in resolving disputes and in clearing ambiguity. It demonstrates that dispute resolution, contractual frameworks and legal awareness impact positively on the adoption of BIM. It also shows that clearly specified BIM protocols are required for effective adoption. Thus, it becomes imperative for project managers to proactively tackle risks for efficiency, meaningful collaboration, and the implementation of project terms.

By so doing, effective planning, successful execution and sustainable safety of construction projects become guaranteed. Insights from the findings of their study make it clear that strategic management of BIM in the course of managing projects using it would produce the desired results expected for the betterment of the research on the legal implications of BIM adoption. The result of EL Mounla's et al. (2023) review of 61 articles on BIM indicate that it produces appreciable innovative results in construction activities and does better when combined with the concept of Lean construction. Thus, the position of the present study on the efficacy of combining BIM with ML and SM for more efficiency in planning, execution and safety of construction projects cannot be disputed.

Like EL Mounla's et al. (2023) study, the present study argues that the combination of the three promises betterment. It follows that this study uniquely contributes to bridging a research gap, as it proposes a better way of planning the successful execution and sustainable safety of construction projects. The study proposes the sustainable combination of machine learning (ML), strategic management (SM) and Building Information Modeling (BIM) in the planning, execution and safety of construction projects so as to achieve breakthroughs. Doing so entails interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary interplay and collaboration between and among professionals in construction, artificial intelligence, information technology, and project management. Then, exchange of knowledge, expertise and services take place consistently.

Salako's (2023) study identifies the strategies for implementing construction management planning. It upholds the view that for a successful execution of projects, effective project management planning tools must be deployed adequately. These include leveraging BIM and other smart technologies like ML for the realization of a successful execution of projects. The planning techniques identified are classic technique and waterfall method, which allow for timely execution of construction projects. The highest challenges to effective planning and execution of construction projects are cost of management

and unfavorable government regulations. Thus, integrating them into the planning processes of construction projects would allow for the realization of project successes. The present study calls for the combination of SM with ML and BIM in the planning of projects so as to attain appreciable success and sustainable safety.

Bagader and Sultan (2022) review some articles on the impact of SM on construction activities in Saudi Arabia. The review proves the existence of a research gap on the ways of achieving sustainable development goals in the construction sector. The study indicates that organizations have to consistently assess and improve their strengths and weaknesses in order to attain considerable performance in the industry. It holds that SM is a mechanism for attaining organizational performance, adopting current innovations and tackling the threats to operations and efficiency. There is no doubt that when combined with ML and BIM, SM would produce more results than those espoused by their study.

Wang and Chen (2023) make a review of some literatures on the integration of BIM and project management in the life cycle of construction. They are of the view that BIM is both a digital construction and management instrument. That is, they argue that apart from playing a critical role in construction, BIM also plays a critical role in the management of construction projects. For them, BIM strengthens the weak life cycle of construction projects. By noting that BIM improves management efficiency in construction projects, Wang and Chen (2023) agree with this study that SM is efficacious in ensuring efficient the planning, execution and safety of construction projects. Its views are apt, justified and sustained by the current study. Beyond their stance, the present study holds the view that BIM can be combined to attain maximal or more beneficial results.

To determine the impact of BIM on the management of construction projects, Hadi (2020) reviewed some previous literatures, emphasizing that the execution of projects begins with planning. As such, it is imperative to combine workable measures like ML, BIM and SM proposed by the current study. While each of them is known to be effective, result-oriented and/or problem-solving, combining the three would mean getting more from them as a result of the combination. Kanyora and Okello (2015) indicate that strategic management is a valuable tool for decision-making, corrective actions and the realization of pursued organizational goals. Drawing evidence from the case of Kenya, their study agrees that construction projects have to be well managed strategically and technologically so as to improve performance, increase the contribution of the construction industry to economy and society, and attain organizational goals. Their study reveals that goal-setting is one major aspect of strategic management that drives planning to execution, as performance is achieved maximally.

For the present study, the strategies include ML, other AI techniques, BM and other smart technologies alongside pragmatic conventional strategies, which have to be blended. Obviously, their study backs the present study by considering or projecting strategic management as a viable mechanism for

achieving targeted organizational and institutional goals. Like others, they do not consider the combination of ML, SM and BIM as viable integrated mechanisms for achieving effective planning and execution of construction projects. That research gap is filled by the present study. This underscores the novelty of the present study.

Conclusion

Indeed, Machine Learning (ML), Building Information Modeling (BIM) and Strategic Management (SM) have the capacity to transform the construction industry respectively. Their collective impact on the industry, when combined, cannot be overemphasized. The study has evidently proven its argument that combining ML, BIM and SM for planning, execution and safety of projects can lead to efficiency at a significant extent. The three systems are integrative, result-oriented and problem-solving pathways to efficient and sustainable planning, execution and safety of construction projects. Imbibing the proposed technology-driven integrative measure would help address issues of efficiency, design, budgeting, projection, decision-making, etc. Stakeholders are charged to increase the adoption of ML, BIM and SM in construction and other like activities. Interdisciplinary collaboration should be practiced among professionals of the concerned endeavors. Training/retraining of manpower would also help a lot.

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